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INTRODUCTION

Through a participatory process, the WP4 “Participatory initiatives in the formulation of policies on soil-based Sustainable Agroecological Systems” intends to define policy strategies to promote soil-based agroecological approaches that fit the recommendations of the European Green Deal, the Mission Board on Soil Health and Food, and the Farm to Fork Strategy.

The present report provides the main results of T4.2 “Participatory processes to involve farmers in the formulation of policies on soil-based Sustainable Agroecological Systems”. It follows D4.1 “Soil-based agroecological policies and measures analysis”, which provided a comprehensive assessment of existing policies and measures dealing with agricultural sustainability while considering agroecological principles in the study regions where the project partners operate.

A participatory design methodology (PDM) was implemented by task partners to deepen the understanding of existing soil-related challenges and explore feasible solutions in these study regions. A detailed description of the method was already provided in guideline M4.2 “Design of the participatory process to involve farmers in the formulation of policies”.

The following sections briefly describe the methodology used to select the case study regions, the PDM process, and data analysis. The results provide information on agricultural soil challenges at the local level, actions expected to help address these challenges, and solutions that can help overcome existing barriers, considering the existing policy framework explored in T4.1. Lessons learned and limitations of the study are finally presented in the conclusion section.

1.1 Research framework

The PDM developed in the present study, to investigate soil-related challenges and policy solutions in agriculture, consists of a two-step approach based on direct interviews with farmers from different study regions, followed by in-depth interviews / focus groups / workshops involving some of the farmers participating in the survey together with agronomists and/or soil scientists. The selection of study regions was guided by the authors' documented knowledge of soil-related challenges existing in the different territories. The interviews were targeted at farmers who were particularly sensitive to the soil challenges mostly represented in the region in which they operate. The second stage of investigation aimed at: discussing the results of the interviews in order to highlight how farmers perceive solutions and barriers; enriching the exploration of possible policy solutions with the opinions of specialists; exploring how policies can contribute to accompany the implementation of the envisaged solutions (e.g., by promoting collective/individual actions). Figure 1 provides the general framework of the study.

Figure 1 – Workflow of the PDM developed in the study

Source: our elaboration based on Burgess et al. (2007)

The data analysis was based on the following procedure. Data from individual surveys in each study region were initially grouped according to farm size. Farm size classes were defined based on a simplified EUROSTAT standard classification, as follows: farms under 20 ha; farms between 20 ha and 70 ha; and farms over 70 ha. These groups were then compared with respect to farmer characteristics (e.g. gender, age, share of income from agriculture) and farm characteristics (e.g. predominant crops, average field slope) in order to create typologies of farming systems and assess whether challenges and constraints are perceived differently by farmers managing different-sized farms. This was followed by a multi-criteria analysis involving stakeholders through the focus groups to explore how existing barriers are being addressed in each case study region. Farmers and experts were first asked to rate the performance of a predefined list of policy solutions with respect to a set of barriers identified in the first step. A synthetic performance score was then calculated using a weighted average of the barrier weights assigned by farmers. Finally, a discussion was held to highlight convergences and divergences of opinion and the alignment between farmers' needs and the societal challenges they influence. This discussion has enriched the understanding of the problem at stake and enabled the interpretation of the quantitative data.

The template for the questionnaires, the description of the study regions and those of results of focus groups were published in the Guidelines Annexes M4.2 "Design of the participatory process to involve farmers in the formulation of policies".

The results of the data analysis in each study region are presented below. This is followed by a brief summary highlighting commonalities and lessons learnt.

1.2 Scope of the study

Table 1 provides an overview of the activities performed by project partners in the study regions. Most of the partners successfully completed both steps of the PDM described above, with the exception of IT and PL. IT was unable to perform the final step of the investigation due to the unavailability of farmers and other stakeholders for the focus groups in the late spring and early summer. Responsible partners have compensated for this inconvenience with additional surveys with a small number of farmers.

Table 1 – Overview of the activities performed by project partners in the study regions.

State	Description of the case study region (Done/Not done)	Farmers' survey (number of interviews)	Focus Group / Workshop / Depth Interview (number of participants)
TR	D	30	121 (WS)
LV	D	10	23 (FG)
LT	D	10	54 (WS)
CZ	D	11	38 (WS)
PL	N	0	0
ES	D	10	17 (FG)
IT	D	10	6 (DI)

Note: TR = Türkiye; LV = Latvia; LT = Lithuania; CZ = Czech Republic; PL = Poland; ES = Spain; IT = Italy.

PL was not able to perform the entire process due to lack of time to dedicate to this task. Nevertheless, the policy domain of PL has been well covered by D4.1, while main adoption barriers are being investigated in T3.3.

The workshop organized in the Turkish study region has involved 17 farmers, 22 policy makers, and 65 advisors and other stakeholders. The workshop organized in the Lithuanian study region involved 12 farmers, 10 policy makers, and 32 advisors and other stakeholders. The focus group organized in the Latvian study region involved 4 farmers, 4 policy makers, and 2 advisors and other stakeholders. The focus group organized in the Spanish study region involved 8 farmers, 3 researchers, 1 policy maker, 1 mayor, 1 innovative farmer, 2 representatives of the largest farmers' association and 1 representative of a major farmer's cooperative. The workshop organized in the Czech study region involved 38 participants. This group consisted of a balanced representation of physical and legal entities, as well as ecological and conventional farmers. From this larger group, 11 key stakeholders were selected for more in-depth involvement. The selection process ensured equal representation across different stakeholder categories

2. SICILY (ITALY)

2.1 Description of the study region

Sicily is the Italian region with the highest risk of desertification¹. Currently, around 56% of the Sicilian agricultural area is under risk of desertification and 35% is under serious threat (SITR, 2015). Every year in Sicily, 117 square kilometres of land turns toward desertification and it becomes unsuitable for life with serious consequences for farmers and the population (Fantappiè, Priori, and Costantini, 2015).

Not all areas of the region are equally affected. The municipalities bordering the Sicilian Channel and those in the Plain of Catania present the highest levels of risk of desertification, which mainly affects areas at an altitude between zero and 200 metres above sea level. Nevertheless, the greatest inconveniences are in the central regions of the island, with special reference to the provinces of Enna and Caltanissetta, where cereal monocultures are widespread and where desertification is accompanied by the abandonment of the territory by the population (Risorgimento Sicilia, 2023).

Farms in this region are medium to large in size, and most are interested in arable lands. The challenge here is to support the conversion of existing agricultural systems into systems that can adapt to climate change and, possibly, reverse desertification. In this context, an association of farmers, research institutions and other stakeholders have recently created the non-profit association '*Semina Diretta 2.0*', which operates throughout southern Italy and has its operational headquarters located in the city of Caltanissetta. The association promotes the diffusion of no-tillage practices to counter soil erosion and the loss of organic matter in arable crops by organizing demonstration campaigns with the contribution of pioneer farmers and training courses. The association has been successful in promoting conservation agriculture, as most of the farmers adopting conservation agriculture practices in Sicily operate in the surrounding area. The association also actively cooperated with the Managing Authority of the 2014-2022 Rurale Development Programme in the design of the agri-environment-climate measures for soil conservation. Nevertheless, the actions promoted by the association, although effective, are still limited to a relatively small area and this might depend on multiple reasons, besides the persistence of knowledge barriers.

2.2 Farmers' challenges and barriers (survey outcome)

Figure 2 provides an overview of the characteristics of the farmers participating in the study and their farms, the soil-health challenges they suffer and the management practices they have adopted to face them. The observations are divided into the three size classes: > 70 ha (large

¹ Desertification in agriculture represents the degradation of soils properties attributable to various causes, including climatic variations and human activities. In practice, desertification manifests as the decrease or disappearance of the biological productivity of cultivated land.

farms) 20-70 ha (medium size farms), < 20 ha (small farms). Specifically, large farms are on average conducted by male farmers, some of whom adopt sustainable production methods, have a higher level of education, employ mainly non-family labour and receive a lower share of income from agriculture than farmers belonging to other classes. Small farms are conducted by female farmers with a low level of education, a low share of income from agriculture and characterized by the prevailing use of family labour. Medium-sized farms are mainly conducted by male farmers with average education, high share of income from agriculture and characterized by a predominant use of family labour (Figure 2 A). Most of the small farms are characterized by mixed farming systems and are in areas with field slopes compared to the other size classes (Figure 2 B).

Farmers conducting large farms are more sensitive to the loss of organic matter, farmers conducting small farms are more sensitive to soil and water pollution, while farmers conducting medium size farms are more sensitive to soil erosion (Figure 2 C). In general, farmers conducting larger farms are better in addressing soil-health issues than other farmers, except for crop diversification management, which is better addressed by farmers conducting small farms.

Figure 2 – Farmer (A) and farm characteristics (B), soil-health challenges (C) and management practices addressing existing challenges (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Sicily, divided into size classes: > 70 ha (green bars); 20-70 ha (yellow bars); < 20 ha (orange bars).

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

Figure 3 provides an overview of the adoption barriers by farm classes. Incompatible market

requirements are particularly addressed by farmers conducting large farms, difficulties to collaborate with other farmers are particularly addressed by farmers conducting medium size farms, lack of equipment is particularly addressed by farmers conducting large farms.

Figure 3 – Adoption barrier for large (A), > 70 ha, medium (B), 20-70 ha, and small farms, < 20 ha (C) and class comparison (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Sicily.

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

2.3 Policy solutions (focus group outcome)

The key challenge is to try to understand what role farmers, both landowners and land managers, can play in the future of the soil and in ensuring its use to allow farming over time. Humans persist in repeating the same farming practices as always, thinking they are adapting the climate to the crop, when the opposite is true. Adaptation should be achieved by changing crops and cropping systems (both species and varieties), but this is not happening.

Conservation agriculture is considered by almost all farmers as a solution to limit both soil compaction and the loss of organic matter. It is also considered important in drought years because it allows surface-developed roots to capture atmospheric moisture found in the surface layer of the soil. Some farmers highlight the relevance of knowledge dissemination to enable proper implementation of this method, which is not merely about tillage management, but requires a complex combination of practices, including the management of crops residues and crop rotation.

For this reason, lack of equipment, although important, is considered by some farmers as a secondary barrier to knowledge dissemination. Farmers do not necessarily need special equipment to implement conservation agriculture. Rather, they should be well trained and supported, especially in the early stages of adoption.

Many farmers apply conservation agriculture only partially, with limited impacts on yield and soil fertility. Crop rotation is particularly overlooked by farmers, mainly due to incompatible market requirements. Conservation agriculture can limit the loss of organic matter, especially in the absence of animal manure.

All of the policy solutions listed in Table 2 are not considered to be particularly relevant for enhancing soil health. In the following, we provide more details on how the barriers and driving forces are differently perceived by farmers and other stakeholders in conditioning the way in which soil-health challenges are faced in the study region.

Table 2 – Policy solutions to face existing challenges for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Sicily. Scores (0 – not effective; 5 – very effective).

	Farms' classes		
	< 20 ha	20 - 70 ha	> 70 ha
Providing incentives to facilitate the adoption of the envisaged solutions	2,70	2,38	1,93
Training advisors and facilitating farmers access to advisory services	0,80	1,37	0,52
Facilitating farmers collaboration on sharing equipment	2,40	2,77	1,65
Facilitating farmers collaboration on coordinating interventions	1,60	2,77	1,35
Funding certification initiatives and awareness campaigns by producers' organizations	0,40	0,45	1,20
Strengthening monitoring, targeting, sanctioning	0,20	1,23	0,93

Source: our elaboration based on policy assessment results from deep interviews.

Coordination barriers - Lack of cooperation between farmers is a key problem raised by most of the farmers who responded to the survey. The difficulty in cooperating with neighboring farms often depends on the fact that conductors are old. Young farmers are willing to cooperate, but they are few because of the low income from agriculture. Often, there is no choice but to rely on contractors, both because of lack of cooperation and lack of seasonal workers. Consequently, the land is gradually abandoned. The absence of cooperation can lead to fire problems in forests because of the absence of herds keeping the forests clean. The absence of fence and control allows overgrazing in other areas, causing problems of soil compaction. Thus, the first issue that needs to be addressed is to facilitate new entrants into agriculture, with special reference to young farmers. This should be followed by recovering the function of the Regional Agricultural Development Agency (ESA), linking farmers with research institutions, guaranteeing training in restoring soil fertility and free access to technical assistance, at last for young and small farmers.

Financial barriers - It is regrettable that the Region has not reconfirmed the RDP intervention in support of conservation agriculture, at a time when farmers are suffering a decrease in direct payments and aids under the national eco-schemes are too low. The Sicilian Region has abolished the support for conservation agriculture because of the lack of applications. This is an unfortunate contingency that cannot justify the suspension of such an important measure.

Knowledge barriers – Lack of knowledge is a very important barrier. There is a great need for training, consultancy and agricultural extension, as the Regional Agricultural Development Agency (ESA) used to do in the recent past. Unfortunately, to date all attempts to provide these services have failed.

Regulatory driving forces – Conservation agriculture is not always fully implementable. There are still no viable alternatives to stubble burning for some cereal crops because of the risk of soil contamination with fungal diseases associated with burying crop residues. Agricultural land left fallow to comply with CAP commitments is subject to soil compaction, requiring great effort to recover the loss fertility.

Market driving forces – Contracts require farmers to guarantee a constant supply of certain products over time, which does not allow farmers to take full advantage of crop rotations. Rotation with leguminous crops is ideal, but there is often no market for the grain obtained from these species. Supporting the development of new value chains by encouraging the cultivation of local specialities or the adoption of certification schemes related to sustainable practices (e.g., organic farming) and/or public procurement initiatives (e.g., school canteens with local food) might encourage crop diversification.

3. ŞANLIURFA, SOUTHEASTERN ANATOLIA (TÜRKIYE)

3.1 Description of the study region

Şanlıurfa province is a rural region where over 64% of the total area is cultivated, and the region plays an important role in influencing Turkey's agricultural policies. The development of agriculture in Şanlıurfa province was successfully promoted since the 1976 with the implementation of the Southeastern Anatolia Project that contributed making it more specialized and export-oriented, also by enhancing the development of irrigation infrastructures. This inadvertently contributed to the spread of unsustainable farming practices.

Here, inadequate drainage management contribute favouring erosion phenomena and the loss of topsoil. Erosion is favored by the runoff from surface irrigation, leading to a depletion of the arable land and the consequent rise the groundwater table and increase salinization, especially in the vital Harran Plain. Approximately 18,000 hectares of this agricultural area reveal the progressive accumulation of salt, with around 150 hectares that are compromised, no longer cultivable. These challenges are compounded by the unregulated use of the region. Addressing these multifaceted challenges requires the design and implementation of a complex mix of measures encompassing the promotion of investments and sustainable farming practices, and stringent environmental regulations to better balance agricultural development with environmental conservation. In Türkiye, sustainable farming is promoted through the IPARD program in selected pilot regions, not including Şanlıurfa Province, despite its strong agricultural vocation.

3.2 Farmers' challenges and barriers (survey outcome)

Figure 4 provides an overview of the characteristics of the farmers that contributed to the study and their farms, the soil-health challenges they suffer and the management practices they adopted to face them. All farms are conducted by male farmers, and they adopt conventional production methods, the use mostly family labor and the income share from agriculture is high. On average large farms have higher education and have higher income share from agriculture than farmers belonging to other classes. Small farms are characterized by the prevailing use of family labor (Figure 2 A). Most of the small farms are characterized by mixed farming systems (Figure 2B).

The perception of soil-health challenges is similar across classes revealing a particular sensitivity to the loss of organic matter and soil and water pollution which are, indeed, both influenced by the excessive use of mineral fertilizers and unsustainable irrigations management (Figure 2C). In general, farmers conducting average size farms perform better in addressing soil-health issues than other farmers, except for fertilizers and pest management, better addressed by farmers conducting small farms.

Figure 4 – Farmers (A) and farms characteristics (B), soil-health challenges (C) and management practices addressing existing challenges (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey

in Şanlıurfa divided into size classes: > 70 ha (green bars); 20-70 ha (yellow bars); < 20 ha (orange bars).

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

Figure 5 provides an overview of the adoption barriers by farm size classes. High implementation costs, followed by incompatible market requirements and lack of equipment, are key barriers across all farm size classes. Lack of advisory services and difficulties in collaborating with other farmers are particularly addressed by farmers conducting medium and small farms.

Figure 5 – Adoption barrier for large (A), > 70 ha, medium (B), 20-70 ha, and small size farms, < 20 ha (C) and class comparison (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Şanlıurfa.

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

3.3 Policy solutions (focus group outcome)

The agricultural sector consistently holds a unique position in the economy. Regarding agricultural products, a comprehensive understanding and awareness are required on a range of issues, including seed selection, irrigation methods, diversity in fertilizer chemistry, the regional characteristics of soil, and precipitation densities. Policymakers should consult farmers at every stage and consider real market conditions when making decisions. Fundamental issues faced by farmers, such as high implementation costs, equipment deficiencies, yield uncertainties, and marketing problems, should be addressed collaboratively with farmers.

In many cases, laws, regulations, and initiatives implemented at the national and regional levels are perceived to have a perverse effect on soil health and an obstacle to farmers' decision-making.

All the policy solutions listed in table 3 are considered extremely relevant in enhancing soil health, as their combination contribute to facing the different barriers farmers suffer and the driving forces farmers are subject to. In the following we provide more details on how the differ barriers and driving forces are perceived by farmers and other stakeholders in conditioning the way in which soil-health challenges are faced in the study region.

Table 3 – Policy solutions to face existing challenges for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Şanlıurfa. Scores (0 – not effective; 5 – very effective).

	Farms' classes		
	< 20 ha	20 - 70 ha	> 70 ha
Providing incentives to facilitate the adoption of the envisaged solutions	4,05	3,98	4,19
Training advisors and facilitating farmers access to advisory services	3,38	3,32	3,45
Facilitating farmers collaboration on sharing equipment	2,04	2,18	1,98
Facilitating farmers collaboration on coordinating interventions	4,24	4,22	4,30

Funding certification initiatives and awareness campaigns by producers' organizations	4,24	4,22	4,30
Strengthening monitoring, targeting, sanctioning	4,18	4,08	4,26

Source: our elaboration based on workshop policy assessment results.

Coordination barriers - The low level of adoption of innovations by producers, the generally small scale of agricultural lands, insufficient agricultural infrastructure, and inadequate organization and cooperatives are significant challenges that constitute the primary obstacles to solving the farmers' issues concerning land. To overcome these challenges, it is necessary to engage farmers in collaborative efforts, ensuring their informed and educated participation.

Financial barriers - The agricultural sector is crucial for people's livelihoods. Until today, the agricultural sector has played a significant role in Turkey's social and economic development. Given its paramount importance, the agricultural sector should receive increased financial support from the government. Farmers struggle to generate sufficient profit due to the high input costs during production. Financially challenged farmers, lacking adequate resources, face difficulties in addressing land-related issues.

Knowledge barriers - Farmers do not possess the necessary skills to implement positive practices related to soil. Occasionally, training programs are organized through public institutions or other non-governmental organizations. However, since participation in these programs is not mandatory, the intended impact is not achieved.

Regulatory driving forces - There is no national/regional restriction to preserve agricultural lands and water resources in the working area. Farmers have the autonomy to decide on their production patterns. However, the region's farmers, who have the habit of cultivating the same crop every year, are unaware that the soil is being exploited and degraded. They attempt to address nutrient deficiencies using chemicals, which are not sustainable. Currently, farmers tend to overuse production inputs. It is necessary to educate farmers on this matter.

Market driving forces - In the working area, the production pattern is determined by the farmers' own volition. Contractual agricultural production practices are rarely implemented. Consequently, farmers prioritize striving for high yields rather than producing high-quality crops. The excessive use of chemicals, water, and other inputs for achieving high yields not only diminishes the quality of the produce but also disrupts the structure of the soil.

4. PROVINCE OF VALENCIA (SPAIN)

4.1 Description of the study region

A total of 301,437 hectares are cultivated in the Province of Valencia in 2023, of which 171,609 ha (56.09%) are irrigated and 129,828 ha (43.06%) are rainfed. The main crops include citrus, fruit trees, vineyards, olives, and cereals (CAPA, 2023). What is significant is that, according to the 2020 Agricultural Census, out of a total of 56,342 farms, 54.8% of them have less than 2 hectares; this figure rises to 79.8% if we consider all farms with less than 5 ha. These owners could not have agriculture as their main activity, due to the low prices of the agricultural products and the important competence of the non-EU markets. On the other hand, medium and large properties are highly specialised and mechanised. Valencian agriculture offers high quality products, and they are very well accepted in the national and European markets, due to the safety controls to which they are subjected, but farmers need wholesalers to reconsider the prices consumers are paying, because sometimes they are even selling their products 'at a loss'. Moreover, in the Province of Valencia, 26.9% of the cultivated area is dedicated to certified organic production by the Committee of Organic Agriculture (CAPA, 2022), highlighting its commitment to sustainable agriculture, compared to the Spanish average of 11% and the European Union average of 10.5%, in 2022 (Eurostat, statistics explained).

The region faces challenges due to the high percentage of mountainous terrain, in the rainfed farming territories, which has required the terrace construction that complicates the mechanization of certain agricultural tasks and increases maintenance costs. Additionally, the territory is characterized by low and irregular yearly precipitations, common in the semi-arid mediterranean climate.

4.2 Farmers' challenges and barriers (survey outcome)

Figure 6 provides an overview of the characteristics of the farmers that contributed to the study and their farms, the soil-health challenges and the management practices they adopted to face them. Farmers belonging to the different farm size classes reveal different characteristics. Farmers conducting medium size and large farms are predominantly male, they mostly use non-family labour, and the income share from agriculture is high. They also formally adopt sustainable production methods, and their education level is high. Small farms are conducted also mainly by male, but the presence of female owners is more common than in big farms, and their education level is high. They mainly use family labor, but the family income share from agriculture is low and very low (Figure 6 A). No mixed farming systems are present and, usually, larger farms reveal the presence of agricultural fields both in the plains (irrigated areas) and in steep slopes (rainfed cultivars) (Figure 6B).

The perception of soil-health challenges is quite different across classes revealing a particular sensitivity to soil erosion and the loss of organic matter by farmers conducting larger farms (Figure 6C). Farmers belonging to the other two classes perceive a broader range of soil-health challenges. In general, farmers conducting large size farms perform better in addressing soil-

health issues than other farmers, with special reference to tillage management but except for fertilizers and pest management, better addressed by farmers conducting average size farms (Figure 6D).

Figure 6 – Farmers (A) and farms characteristics (B), soil-health challenges (C) and management practices addressing existing challenges (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Valencia divided into size classes: > 70 ha (green bars); 20-70 ha (yellow bars); < 20 ha (orange bars).

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

Figure 7 provides an overview of the adoption barriers by farm classes. Lack of technical support is perceived particularly important by farmers conducting larger farms. Incompatible market requirements (caliber, visual presence, price, etc.) are considered more important by farmers belonging to the other classes.

Figure 7 – Adoption barrier for large (A), > 70 ha, medium (B), 20-70 ha, and small size farms, < 20 ha (C) and class comparison (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in the Province of Valencia.

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

4.3 Policy solutions (focus group outcome)

The group of farmers participating in the survey revealed the difficulties in adopting conservation and organic agriculture partly because of the uncertain potentialities of the method, and, above all, pest management and post-harvest product conservation using also organic products. They also consider that local and national consumers do not demand enough organic products, and 80% of the production is exported to Northern European countries.

Most of the policy solutions listed in table 4 are not considered relevant in enhancing soil health by the group of farmers participating in the survey. In the following, we provide more details on how the differ barriers and driving forces are perceived by farmers and other stakeholders in conditioning the way in which soil-health challenges are faced in the study region.

Table 4 – Policy solutions to face existing challenges for the group of farmers participating in the survey in the Province of Valencia. Scores (0 – not effective; 5 – very effective).

	Farms' classes		
	< 20 ha	20 - 70 ha	> 70 ha
Providing incentives to facilitate the adoption of the envisaged solutions	2,37	2,45	2,60
Training advisors and facilitating farmers access to advisory services	1,04	0,80	1,95

Facilitating farmers collaboration on sharing equipment	1,91	2,05	2,20
Facilitating farmers collaboration on coordinating interventions	2,83	2,95	2,55
Funding certification initiatives and awareness campaigns by producers' organizations	1,61	1,50	1,45
Strengthening monitoring, targeting, sanctioning	1,22	1,15	1,35

Source: our elaboration based on policy assessment results from deep interviews.

Coordination barriers – New market rules are needed to guarantee a fair distribution of the income across value chain actors and to engage all the relevant stakeholders in addressing soil health and sustainability.

Financial barriers – Farmers' incomes decline over time because of increasing input prices that are not compensated for by revenues. Such a condition makes small size farmers abandon the land. In rain-fed agricultural areas, most of the fields are located on sloping hillsides, requiring significant economic input to maintain the dry-stone terraces, which are highly exposed to the effects of torrential rains.

Knowledge barriers – Large farms are very interested in improving their knowledge and the sustainability of their production methods, but they need more evidence and training to drive the required changes. In any case, these farmers often have agronomists to advise them on new developments. Small and medium-sized landowners infrequently attend courses run by advisory services, sometimes because they are held far away from their municipality.

Regulatory driving forces – Potential buyers are looking for large plots of land to make the investment profitable. In the Province of Valencia, small properties predominate, which is why many small, scattered farms, are being abandoned (due to the lack of generational succession in small farms), as it is not possible to achieve a sufficient farm size, which discourages potential buyers. On the other hand, the use of pesticides is not enough regulated. They have also important problems with the water use for irrigation, due to the long drought periods and the important extension of the irrigated areas. Macro-policies urgently need to be adapted to the needs of the territory in the design of micro-policies (at regional and local level).

Market driving forces – Medium size and small farmers are strongly influenced by market forces which are not considered fair. There is significant competition from products from Africa and South America, and farmers and consumers are demanding that they be required to comply with the same food safety measures as European Union producers.

5. VIDZEME (LATVIA)

5.1 Description of the study region

The region is in the boreal/hemi boreal bioclimatic zone, where the annual amount of precipitation of 685 mm exceeds evaporation (Kļaviņš et al., 2016). Agricultural activities have experienced some decline since 1990. Almost 30.5% of the territory in the region is farmland. 14.5% of the farmland in the area is cultivated under organic farming (Official Statistics of Latvia, 2022) and is populated both by small family farms and very large farm holdings.

Currently, 40% of Latvia's agricultural soils are characterized by high levels of acidity, necessitating the application of lime to achieve optimal yields for protein crops and other agricultural produce (Kreišmane et al., 2016). The amount of lime needed to neutralize soil acidity from fertilizers depends on the type and application rates of the fertilizers. Liming acidic soil is essential to allow farming but it causes nutrient leaching. Farmers face multiple barriers in liming management, including technology, environment, and economics. Technologically, there is limited access to modern tools like precision machinery, necessitating the development of affordable services. Environmentally, information gaps about various liming materials and the need for controlled magnesium and calcium content in soil complicate the selection and application of liming materials. Economically, the high cost and long payback period of liming makes it a practice that can be implemented in the areas with the greatest production potential (Popluga and Kreišamane, 2020). Currently, liming is subsidized by the CAP through the eco-scheme instruments (LAD, 2023).

5.2 Farmers' challenges and barriers (survey outcome)

Figure 8 provides an overview of the characteristics of the farmers that contributed to the study and their farms, the soil-health challenges they suffer and the management practices they adopted to face them. Farmers belonging to the different farm size classes reveal different characteristics. Large farms are mainly conducted by male farmers, they use also non-family labor, the income share from agriculture is high and they formally adopt conventional production methods. On the opposite small farm are mainly conducted by female farmers with high education levels, they adopt sustainable production methods. In addition, the income share from agriculture is very low and they take advantage of non-family labor. The use of family labor is dominant in average size farm classes (Figure 8 A). Small farms implement mixed farming systems, and the share of permanent grassland is higher because of the presence of livestock (Figure 8 B).

The perception of soil-health challenges is quite similar across classes revealing a particular sensitivity to soil acidification issues. In addition, farmers conducting large size farms perceive soil and water pollution more important than other farmers, also considering the difficulties they have in managing fertilization (Figure 8 C and 8 D). Tillage management is particularly problematic for small farms, but the key issue is about mechanization management which is found to negatively affect soil-health in most of the farms because of the use of heavy machines

that causes soil compaction (Figure 8 D).

Figure 8 – Farmers (A) and farms characteristics (B), soil-health challenges (C) and management practices addressing existing challenges (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Vidzeme divided into size classes: > 70 ha (green bars); 20-70 ha (yellow bars); < 20 ha (orange bars).

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

Figure 9 provides an overview of the adoption barriers by farm classes. High implementation costs followed yield uncertainty are perceived particularly important by farmers conducting larger farms. Incompatible market requirements by farmers conducting medium size farms and lack of equipment are considered more important by farmers conducting small farms.

Figure 9 – Adoption barrier for large (A), > 70 ha, medium (B), 20-70 ha, and small size farms, < 20 ha (C) and class comparison (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Vidzeme.

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

5.3 Policy solutions (focus group outcome)

All the policy solutions listed in table 5 are not considered relevant in enhancing soil health, as their combination does not really contribute to facing the different barriers farmers suffer and the driving forces farmers are subject to.

The general opinion in the seminar was that if we are comparing Latvia to the rest of the Europe, there are no significant soil degradation risks in Latvia. We have problems with nutrient balance (including leaching etc.), decrease of soil organic matter and organic carbon, and acidification, and increase in soil moisture (degradation of melioration and drainage systems, as well as due to road construction etc.), but maintaining nutrient elements in the soil and liming is in principle in the farmer's own interest, as it brings more profit later and they do that without specific directions from the EU. In addition, if serious soil improvement is required to obtain an economically viable crop, it must be asked whether such land is even worth using for agriculture. In principle, the type of production (crops, grass, etc.) should be managed on the appropriate soil.

Until now, the implemented programs for soil improvement have not always produced the intended results. For example, the use of catch crops for greening the soil did not help to attract a significant amount of nitrogen to the soil. Farmers also had to fertilize their fields additionally. Also, when giving a tool - soil greening measures - without explaining to the farmer the interaction of such a political tool with other soil and production processes, there is no

understanding of the need for related activities. For example, additional measurements, correction of mineral dosage and maintenance of current information after each new period. Also, scientific studies on the effectiveness of the tool, which are relevant for a specific country. Currently, agronomists take a lot of information about current agricultural practices and their implementation from foreign countries, which is only partially suitable for Latvia's situation. The introduction of any new tool requires adequate education of both advisors and farmers about the interaction of the tool with existing practices. It is necessary to implement a specific common direction that covers all stakeholders related to agriculture.

Minimal ploughing was given as another example of how political instruments do not always correspond to the specific country's needs. Every country has a different situation, Latvia has heavier soils compared to the Europe. If the soil is not ploughed, it compacts and not only due to the use of heavy equipment, but also purely naturally during the calm period in late autumn and winter with rain and snow. In the central and southern part of Europe, there are completely different climatic, economic and soil conditions, therefore minimal tillage works. In the north it is necessary not only to plough, but also to periodically deep plough to prevent the formation of a compacted arum sole.

Table 5 – Policy solutions to face existing challenges for the group of farmers participating in the survey in Vidzeme. Scores (0 – not effective; 5 – very effective).

	Farms' classes		
	< 20 ha	20 - 70 ha	> 70 ha
Providing incentives to facilitate the adoption of the envisaged solutions	2,28	2,75	2,57
Training advisors and facilitating farmers access to advisory services	1,03	1,55	1,30
Facilitating farmers collaboration on sharing equipment	2,80	2,13	2,03
Facilitating farmers collaboration on coordinating interventions	2,07	1,48	1,90
Funding certification initiatives and awareness campaigns by producers' organizations	0,98	1,68	1,53
Strengthening monitoring, targeting, sanctioning	0,35	0,45	0,27

Source: our elaboration based on focus group policy assessment results.

In the following we provide more details on how the differ barriers and driving forces are perceived by farmers and other stakeholders in conditioning the way in which soil-health challenges are faced in the study region.

Coordination barriers - The development of production and the solution of environmental and soil quality issues require the coordinated action of all parties - perhaps even a single institution is needed. Problems should be solved in both directions with a common goal, this is the most effective way and if the farmers' cooperation will have an economic basis, then it will also determine the need or lack of cooperation. However, creating artificial cooperation is not necessary. On the other hand, the institutes believe that the creation of regional communities

should be realized in order to promote circulation, cooperation, resource exchange, where all involved benefit, are energetically independent and are not affected by market fluctuations. Latvia has historically had homestead agriculture, where each farmer solves problems individually and mutual cooperation is determined by their own motivation. This applies especially to large farmers who manage up to 5,000 ha of arable land and are self-sufficient or have already gathered a professional team around them to help solve problems and make appropriate decisions. In this case, cooperation and knowledge sharing between consultants and agronomists belonging to such different teams should be encouraged. Farmers' cooperation is more economically beneficial for small farmers who cultivate less than 100 ha of land, because the attraction of large external investments in small farms is not as economically profitable and does not pay off as quickly as it is in large farms. In such a case, farmers cooperate with their close neighbours both in terms of agricultural machinery and information, as well as in terms of useful contacts. The biggest problem in Latvia is cooperation between policy makers at the national level and farmers. There is no common vision or direction towards a common goal when we talk about soil and agriculture as national wealth and irreplaceable resources. Policymakers should coordinate more with scientists and farmers before incorporating EU regulations into national legislation, providing appropriate solutions for the appropriate situation, rather than adapting everything that Europe dictates. Another issue is communication, whether public institutions and the private sector work in harmony and are aware of each other's existence. The information flow between institutions and private actors in Latvia is quite poor and should be improved.

Financial barriers - All participants of the seminar agree that state subsidies are not enough in any case, but it is also necessary to manage farming without state subsidies. At the moment there is not really direct support aimed at soil conservation, maybe it is partially included in various programs, but does the farmer see it as compensation for soil conservation? The representatives of the institutions emphasize that farmers need knowledge, therefore state subsidies are more necessary for scientific research. The fact that the common agricultural policy is dictated by the large EU member states, which have different problems than in Latvia, is also indicated as a problem. A particularly big obstacle that is difficult to overcome is the large bureaucracy that revolves around subsidies and other financial resources. Reporting systems are too complex, they should be simplified. It would also require an individual risk assessment for each farmer individually to apply the best subsidies, however, this runs into problems at the middle stage of this system, which are the distributors and controllers of the subsidies. Not only is there a lack of human resources, but also the subsidy payment systems change every season and not only for farmers, but it is also difficult for state employees to follow all the changes coming from Europe.

Knowledge barriers - Farmers have knowledge gaps to implement policies. Farmers of different scales have very different understandings. Also, the fact that farmers are in different age groups that perceive information and technological opportunities from a different point of view. If the farmer is not interested in learning new skills, then improving the availability of knowledge will do nothing, so it is necessary to promote the interest of farmers in learning new things, popularize decisions based on research (field, economic). Farming advisors should be the first

ones that are educated about soil degradation so they can pass the knowledge to farmers in understandable language. This is because farmers are not keen to participate in seminars organised by government and official advisors, they choose to go to demonstration farms, small farmers brainstorm with neighbours, big farmers hire professional agrochemists that are not educated in soil degradation but more in how to improve harvest. Every stakeholder involved in the agricultural policy – from policy makers to farmer need to find common language level, that is understandable to everyone, then there will be motivation to learn innovative practices and to use the tools that are given to farmers from above. Right now, 50-year-old farmers do not care about emissions of carbon farming because they simply do not understand the information that comes along with the paperwork. This might be connected to the quality of education farmers receive in university, not everyone with a degree has the knowledge needed to be a successful and environmentally friendly farmer. So, maybe this problem should be solved at the root.

Regulatory driving forces - Restrictions exist, they are included in the law, but it is not enough to solve the problems. At present, the restrictions limit without scientific justification, they are not properly researched and approved, therefore they are incomprehensible and illogical to farmers. There are some laws that provide soil protection, however most of the restrictions are disproportionate to the problem or its solution and go against agricultural production practices. A big problem is that funding is not going to the direction where it is needed, but in the direction where it is popular, for example, carbon sequestration, which is a wide problem with a lot of funding, but there is no properly evaluated methodology with which to study, with which to evaluate and how and to whom funding is allocated. In the current situation, where everyone is doing what they want and there are no uniform guidelines for either methods or evaluation, the research results are different and biased. They are not valid in principle to arrive at a concrete and usable result in the end.

Market driving forces - On the contrary, in Latvia there are agreements on driving forces that directly help in the fight against soil degradation - eco-schemes, support for organic agriculture, etc. However, this support is small and would not be effective without the initiative of the farmer himself.

6. WESTERN LITHUANIA

6.1 Description of the study region

The area belongs to boreal/hemi boreal bioclimatic zone, typical climate is maritime with mild, wet winters and cool, humid summers. The agricultural area constitutes 46.92 % of the territory. 76% of the agricultural area is arable land, followed by 22% of meadows and pastures (Galvonaitė, 2013). The region is populated by both small family farms and very large farm holdings.

The main threats to soil in Western Lithuania are nutrient imbalance, soil compaction, and acidification. The excess of inorganic nitrogen and phosphorous fertilizers are dramatically impacting surface and groundwater pollution. Soil compaction is an increasing problem due to the use of heavy machinery. About 40.28 % of the agricultural land in the area is susceptible to soil compaction. Soil acidification is a critical problem mainly influenced by natural processes. Approximately 19% of the soil is in accelerated acid conditions, about 1 million ha are at risk of chemical degradation by acidification and this number is increasing. Policy instruments are available to face existing challenges, but they need to be better tailored to regional needs and differentiated accordingly.

6.2 Farmers' challenges and barriers (survey outcome)

Figure 10 provides an overview of the characteristics of the farmers that contributed to the study and their farms, the soil-health challenges they suffer and the management practices they adopted to face them. The average size farm class is not represented by the farmers participating in the survey for this study region. Farmers belonging to the different farm size classes reveal different characteristics. Small farms are mainly conducted by female farmers, and they formally adopt sustainable production methods, and they use mainly family labor but the share of family income from agriculture is very low. On the other hand, large farms are mainly conducted by male farmers adopting conventional production methods, using also non-family labour, and the prevailing family income comes from agriculture (Figure 8A). Small farms implement mixed farming systems (Figure 8 B).

The perception of soil-health challenges is quite similar across classes revealing a particular sensitivity to soil compaction and soil and water pollution (Figure 8 C). Mechanization management is found to negatively affect soil-health in most of the farms because of the use of heavy machines that causes soil compaction (Figure 8 D).

Figure 10 – Farmers (A) and farms characteristics (B), soil-health challenges (C) and management practices addressing existing challenges (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in western Lithuania divided into size classes: > 70 ha (green bars); 20-70 ha (yellow bars); < 20 ha (orange bars).

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

Figure 11 provides an overview of the adoption barriers by farm classes. High implementation costs are considered important by all farmers. Incompatible market requirements is considered important by farmers conducting large farms, while lack of equipment is considered more important by farmers conducting small farms. Lack of advisory services is also an important barrier for large farms.

Figure 11 – Adoption barrier for large (A), > 70 ha, medium (B), 20-70 ha, and small size farms, < 20 ha (C) and class comparison (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in western Lithuania.

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

6.3 Policy solutions (focus group outcome)

Focus group stakeholders agree in considering that that laws, regulations, and initiatives implemented at the national and regional levels are mostly oriented to ecological factors, not agricultural. This issue raises obstacles for sustainable development. Indeed, agricultural policies support more the purchase of inputs (seeds, pesticides, fertilizers, fuel) rather than the renewal of the equipment. Farmers are highly motivated to implement innovative solutions, and new know-how technologies, but there are financial barriers and lack of policies to overcome them that block development.

Table 6 provides information about the policy solution that can help overcome existing barriers. It appears evident the need to strengthening, monitoring, sanctioning and targeting, with special reference to targeting as stakeholders denounce the lack of support for a sustainable development.

Table 6 – Policy solutions to face existing challenges for the group of farmers participating in the survey in western Lithuania. Scores (0 – not effective; 5 – very effective).

	Farms' classes		
	< 20 ha	20 - 70 ha	> 70 ha
Providing incentives to facilitate the adoption of the envisaged solutions	3,63	N.D.	3,59
Training advisors and facilitating farmers access to advisory services	3,60	N.D.	3,28
Facilitating farmers collaboration on sharing equipment	2,20	N.D.	2,54
Facilitating farmers collaboration on coordinating interventions	3,48	N.D.	3,73
Funding certification initiatives and awareness campaigns by producers' organizations	3,93	N.D.	3,99
Strengthening monitoring, targeting, sanctioning	4,60	N.D.	4,48

Notes: N.D. = Note Defined

Source: our elaboration based on focus group policy assessment results.

As proof of that, agricultural land located in protected areas tends to be abandoned. In this regard more collaboration between farmers Unions and policy makers is highly suggested.

In the following we provide more details on how the differ barriers and driving forces are perceived by farmers and other stakeholders in conditioning the way in which soil-health challenges are faced in the study region.

Coordination barriers - There is a lack of dialogue between policy makers and farmers unions. Regarding agricultural products, a comprehensive understanding and awareness are required on a range of issues, including national market formation, export questions, adaptation to changing climate (new pests and diseases, new fertilization methods). Policymakers should consult farmers at every stage and consider real market conditions when making decisions. Fundamental issues faced by farmers: high risk of farms budgets (regards uncertainty of environmental conditions), rising implementation costs, unclear regional macro-economic and political conditions, and marketing problems, should be addressed collaboratively with farmers.

Financial barriers - The agricultural sector is crucial for people to sustain their lives. Until today, the agricultural sector has played a significant role in Lithuanian's social and economic development. But nowadays farmers struggle to generate sufficient profit due to the high input costs during production. Public subsidies are not adequate for the costs of agroecological strategies implementation. There is a lack of knowledge of new strategies and possibilities.

Knowledge barriers - Farmers are highly motivated and have necessary skills to implement positive practices related to soil. Training programs are organized through public institutions or other non-governmental organizations (farmer unions etc.). However, there is a lack of knowledge in law and potential funding schemes.

Regulatory driving forces - There is national/regional restriction to preserve agricultural lands and water resources in the working area (encouraging to restore peats, long terms pastures). If farmers want to get subsidies, they have no autonomy to decide on their production patterns. These restrictions lead to cutting the activities in protected areas.

Market driving forces - Market mainly based on export prices which are regulated by the international EURONEXT market. Local market driving forces (local markets, shops, ferries) are not significant.

7. WESTERN CZECH REPUBLIC

7.1 Description of the study region

The structure of land use in the Czech Republic is characterized by forested and agricultural areas, more than one-third of the Czech land (33.8% in 2015) is forest and more than half is agricultural land (53.4%). Half of the agricultural land is located in areas which are less favourable for farming (LFA areas) and these are the very areas which support the creation and maintenance of meadows and pastures.

The greatest problem for land use protection is land take and soil sealing, with special reference to the western region. The conversion of farmland to urban uses represents a very serious problem. The forced collectivization of the 1950's has significantly damaged the relationship of owners to their land. Nowadays, 74% of fields are leased and sometimes it is only managed for short-term profit. This poses several soil-related issues. Excessive mineral fertilization, due to the low price of nitrogen fertilizers and the lack of organic matter, contributed to compromising soil quality (around 26% of the agricultural land is characterized by an excessive acidity). Soil acidification is particularly relevant in the study region with special reference to Karlovy Vary and South Bohemia, followed by the Vysočina and the Pilsen territory. Soil compaction is more widespread in the country, and it makes the agricultural land more vulnerable to extreme climatic events and water erosion. Because of the relevance of soil compaction, the Ministry of Agriculture, in cooperation with the Research Institute for Soil and Water Conservation (RISWC), enacted the Manual for Protection against Water Erosion for farmers and smallholders. Most importantly, recently the government started implementing a land consolidation reform interesting 25% of the agricultural land of the country. This involves new property right rules to align land ownership and land management and new rules for land management with the aim of contributing to increasing the ecological stability of the landscape.

7.2 Farmers' challenges and barriers (survey outcome)

Figure 12 provides an overview of the characteristics of the farmers that contributed to the study and their farms, the soil-health challenges they suffer and the management practices they adopted to face them. Farmers belonging to the different farm size classes reveal different characteristics. Small farms are mainly conducted by female farmers, and they formally adopt sustainable production methods, but the share of family income from agriculture is very low. On the opposite large farm are mainly conducted by male farmers adopting conventional production methods, using mainly non-family labour, and the prevailing family income comes from agriculture (Figure 12 A). Medium size farms are mainly conducted by family farms and the prevailing family income is from agriculture. Small farms implement mixed farming systems followed by medium size farms (Figure 12 B).

The perception of soil-health challenges is quite similar across classes revealing a particular sensitivity to soil acidification (Figure 12 C). Soil and water pollution is particularly addressed by farmers conducting large farms, while the loss of organic matter by farmers conducting medium

size farms (Figure 12 D).

Figure 12 – Farmers (A) and farms characteristics (B), soil-health challenges (C) and management practices addressing existing challenges (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in western Czech Republic divided into size classes: > 70 ha (green bars); 20-70 ha (yellow bars); < 20 ha (orange bars).

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

Figure 13 provides an overview of the adoption barriers by farm classes. High implementation costs are considered important by all farmers. Incompatible market requirements and yield uncertainty are considered important by farmers conducting large and medium size farms, while lack of equipment is considered more important by farmers conducting small farms.

Figure 13 – Adoption barrier for large (A), > 70 ha, medium (B), 20-70 ha, and small size farms, < 20 ha (C) and class comparison (D) for the group of farmers participating in the survey in western Czech Republic.

Source: our elaboration based on *ad hoc* surveys.

7.3 Policy solutions (focus group outcome)

Since the entrance of the Czech Republic into the EU and the adoption of the commitment of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) the Czech agriculture undergo deep structural and regional changes. The CAP exposed Czech agriculture to uneven competition with other farmers in the EU. As a result, the output of the agricultural sector decreased, livestock farms have decreased as well as the arable land. On the other hand, many non-productive and non-agricultural activities in the rural areas brought new opportunities for farmers.

Table 7 provides an overview of the policy solutions that can contribute facing existing soil-health challenges and promoting a sustainable development of regional agriculture. The main barriers that counter a sustainable development are structural nature. The Czech agriculture is radically based on large-scale production. Lack of collaboration is also considered as very important, with special reference to the interface between farmers' Union / policy makers.

Table 7 – Policy solutions to face existing challenges for the group of farmers participating in the survey in western Czech Republic. Scores (0 – not effective; 5 – very effective).

	Farms' classes		
	< 20 ha	20 - 70 ha	> 70 ha
Providing incentives to facilitate the adoption of the envisaged solutions	2,72	2,53	2,43

Training advisors and facilitating farmers access to advisory services	4,87	4,85	4,80
Facilitating farmers collaboration on sharing equipment	4,28	4,15	4,27
Facilitating farmers collaboration on coordinating interventions	4,05	4,25	4,07
Funding certification initiatives and awareness campaigns by producers' organizations	3,22	3,40	3,47
Strengthening monitoring, targeting, sanctioning	2,98	2,98	2,93

Notes: N.D. = Note Defined

Source: our elaboration based on workshop policy assessment results.

In the following we provide more details on how the different barriers and driving forces are perceived by farmers and other stakeholders in conditioning the way in which soil-health challenges are faced in the study region.

Coordination barriers - Joint coordination is required to drive the selection of the required interventions.

Financial barriers - Inflation and rising prices of inputs made the financial support less effective in recent years.

Knowledge barriers – Training and knowledge dissemination is not well supported. Counseling services are not sufficiently developed as in other countries. Farmers applying for payments are now required to attend training courses.

Regulatory driving forces - There are national/regional regulations to preserve agricultural lands. A stricter version of the soil protection law is being prepared with special reference to soil sealing. The amendment primarily proposes a ban on the construction of large shopping and logistics centers with an area of more than one hectare on the highest quality land. The ban would also apply to standard photovoltaic power plants.

Market driving forces - Czech agriculture is significantly influenced by international market forces that mostly drive the development of the agricultural sector.

8. LESSONS LEARNT FROM THE STUDY REGIONS

With the present report we provided some basic descriptive statistic to summarize the information collected with direct surveys in the study regions and qualitative information to support the interpretation for the two step multicriteria policy solution exercise described in the guidelines report of Milestone 4.2. 'Design of the participatory process to involve farmers in the formulation of policies.

Although not explicitly mentioned, all expert groups perceive the influence of policy as essential in shaping farming systems, as policy is nothing more than the instrument through which the social system legitimises challenges and actions.

Agriculture is a strategic sector in all the study regions investigated in T4.2 and T1.2. The characteristics of the dominant farming systems are very different across study regions. Sometimes small farms are found to be more likely to be conducted with sustainable production methods, sometimes large farms. Thus, the formal adoption of sustainable production methods is not found to be influenced by the size of the farm.

Land use rules are a very important issue addressed by most of stakeholders participating in the study across the different study regions. Albeit in different ways, land use rules influence the distribution of the agricultural land across farm typologies and across different uses. We collected some evidence regarding the absence of adequate rules to avoid land grabbing in some areas, with special reference to CZ, due to the low prices of the land and the lack of regulation on property right in favor of local farmers, and access to land in other areas, such as ES, due to the high land prices accompanied with low support to new entrants and young farmers.

This is nothing but a marginal issue considering that large farms are usually characterized by the prevalence of non-family labor, while small farms by the low family income share from agriculture, factors that appear to contribute both to negatively influencing farmers sensitivity to soil health challenges, regardless of the production method they formally adopt. Thus, the combination of high income share from agriculture and the prevailing use of family labor are being found the factors that mostly contribute influencing farmers willingness to face existing soil-health challenges, at least in the group of farmers and other stakeholders participating in the study. These are the two enabling conditions to guarantee a radical and prompt adaptation to existing challenges.

Even knowledge creation and dissemination are secondary to the above factors, as young farmers conducting family farms affect its relevance as they are more prone to innovate, they are more sensitive to the environment in which they operate, they require new knowledge services.

Environmental and agricultural regulation are also important, although they need to be integrated into a coherent land use policy framework. Their reliance is essentially of a social nature as they contribute conditioning farmers roles and can have positive or negative effects

depending on how they are designed. For instance, the lack of environmental regulation is found to contribute to facilitating the overexploitation of agricultural soils in some areas, such as TR, while severe environmental restriction not supported by adequate financial measures can facilitate land abandonment in other areas, such as LV.

Finally, market forces contribute to shaping farming systems, farmers networks and farmers' needs. The high specialization of the farming systems that characterize most of farms investigated with this study from the different study regions influence their dependence on external inputs, their difficulties to manage soil fertility because of the absence of livestock and the reduction of cooperation, also due to the old age of neighbor farmers and the loss of synergies brought by excessive specialization of entire agricultural territories.

More sophisticated approaches to summarize quantitative and qualitative information have been developed as a follow up of this study and presented as a poster at the EJP SOIL Annual Science Day 2024 with the title 'Soil health challenges and farmers' adaptation strategies: transition pathways in Türkiye and the European Union' and at the 2024 IFSA conference with the title 'Participatory initiatives to promote soil-based agroecological principles'.

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